

Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with N-Hydroxy-N-*p*-chlorophenyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-*p*-toluamidine Hydrochloride and Some Phenols

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A simple, convenient and highly selective method for extractive-photometric determination of micro amount of vanadium(V) has been developed. It is based on the reaction of N-hydroxy-N-*p*-chlorophenyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-*p*-toluamidine hydrochloride with vanadium(V) to give 1 : 2 complex and its extraction as 1 : 1 adducts in presence of phenols. The effective molar absorptivities lie in the range 6500-7000 $l \cdot mole^{-1} \cdot cm^{-1}$. Many common ions such as Mo^{6+} , Cu^{2+} , Zr^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , Ag^+ , Zn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , W^{6+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Al^{3+} do not interfere and method is accurately applied for determination of vanadium in BCS steels.

In recent years, synergic extraction of vanadium(V) employing a monobasic and bidentate chelating agent in the presence of an adduct forming substance¹⁻⁵ or an anion⁶⁻⁹ has received considerable attention as the extracts are highly stable in organic solvents and can be utilised for spectrophotometric determination of vanadium content of steels¹⁰ and atomic absorption spectrometric determination of vanadium¹¹. The extractive-photometric method reported in the recent communication employing N-hydroxy-N-*p*-chlorophenyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-*p*-toluamidine hydrochloride (a newly synthesised monobasic and bidentate chelating agent containing hydroxyamidine functional grouping¹²⁻¹⁵ and some phenols is very rapid and equals in sensitivity to the methods reported by Kojima *et al*¹¹ and Rao *et al*¹⁰. Moreover, in the present method, which is highly selective, molar absorptivities of the vanadium adducts do not increase even if phenol concentration is increased above optimal concentration. The proposed method has been applied to the estimation of vanadium content of some standard steels.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Absorption spectra were recorded with a Carl-Zeiss 'Specord', ultraviolet-visible recording spectrophotometer was employed for absorbance measurements. Systronic pH meter type-322 was used for pH determinations.

Reagents :

N-Hydroxy-N-*p*-chlorophenyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-*p*-toluamidine hydrochloride (HCPMCPH) was prepared by condensing

equimolar quantities of N-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-*p*-toluimidoyl chloride and N-*p*-chlorophenyl-hydroxylamine in ether according to the method of Deb and Mishra¹⁶. White shining crystals of the compound were obtained upon crystallisation from absolute ethanol containing few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. M.P., 164°; yield, 73% (Found : C, 59.70; H, 4.35; N, 6.26%. $C_{21}H_{15}N_2OCl_3$ requires C, 59.78; H, 4.51; N, 6.64%). A 0.2% (0.006M) solution of HCPMCPH and a 0.2M solution of phenol in chloroform was used for extraction purposes.

Standard solution of vanadium(V) was prepared by dissolving ammonium-metavanadate (B.D.H., A.R.) in double distilled water and the solution standardised volumetrically¹⁷.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure :

A suitable aliquot (5-10 ml) of the solution containing 100 μg of vanadium(V) was placed in a separatory funnel (60 ml). It was diluted to 25 ml with water and the pH was adjusted to the desired value (Table 1) with dilute hydrochloric acid and ammonia. Chloroform solutions of the reagent and phenol (each 5 ml) were added and the two phases were vigorously equilibrated for 1 min. The organic phase was separated and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. To ensure complete recovery of vanadium, the aqueous layer was washed with 2 $\times$ 4 ml portions of chloroform and the extract mixed with the main solution. The combined extracts were diluted to 25 ml in a volumetric flask and the absorbance was measured at λ_{max} against chloroform.

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TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF VANADIUM-HCPMCPH COMPLEX IN THE PRESENCE OF PHENOLS

Phenol	pH ranges for complete extraction	Optimum conc. ranges from Beer's law ppm of V	Optimum conc. ranges from Ringbom plot ^a ppm of V	λ_{max} nm	ϵ , 1.mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g of V cm}^{-2}$	Relative standard deviation ^a
—	3.0	—	—	565	700	—	—
Phenol	1.2-4.0	0.5-6.4	1.0-6.0	590	7000	0.0072	± 0.70
<i>o</i> -Cresol	1.1-4.0	0.8-0.7	1.2-6.4	595	6500	0.0080	± 0.72
<i>m</i> -Cresol	1.2-4.2	0.8-6.6	1.2-6.2	590	6700	0.0075	± 0.58
<i>p</i> -Cresol	1.3-4.2	0.6-6.6	1.0-6.0	595	6800	0.0074	± 0.65

^a = 10 determinations are made with samples each containing 80 μg of V/25 ml.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectra :

The absorption spectra of vanadium-HCPMCPH complex and its phenol adducts are shown in Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra :

- (—○—○—○—) Vanadium ($7.56 \times 10^{-5} M$) + HCPMCPH (0.003 M) + phenol (0.03).
- (—●—●—●—) Vanadium ($7.56 \times 10^{-5} M$) + HCPMCPH (0.003 M).
- (—○—○—○—) Vanadium ($7.56 \times 10^{-5} M$) + phenol (0.03M).
- (—○—○—○—) HCPMCPH (0.003M) in chloroform.

and the relevant data are presented in Table 1. The vanadium-HCPMCPH complex shows maximum absorbance at 550-580 nm having the value for molar absorptivity to be 700 1.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. In presence of phenols a hyper- and bathochromic effect is observed. Thus, the blue adducts show absorption maxima at 590-595 nm with molar absorptivities ranging between 6500 and 7000 1.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Choice of Solvent for Extraction Work :

Several organic solvents such as chloroform, benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, chlorobenzene, *o*-dichlorobenzene, etc., quantitatively extracted the vanadium adducts from aqueous phase. However, chloroform was selected for the present

studies because of the higher solubility of HCPMCPH in it than in other solvents and its high extractability towards the vanadium complexes.

Effect of pH :

The vanadium adducts were quantitatively extracted into organic phase from solutions adjusted at pH around 1.2-4.0. Beyond this limit percentage extraction of vanadium decreased.

Amount and Order of Addition of Reagents :

The extraction of vanadium-HCPMCPH-phenol adducts are independent of order of addition of HCPMCPH or phenol. A 3 fold molar excess of HCPMCPH is adequate for complete extraction of vanadium in presence of 400 fold molar excess of phenol. A 40 and 1000 fold molar excess of HCPMCPH and phenol respectively has no influence on the net absorbance of the complexes.

Effect of Volume of Aqueous Phase, Time, Temperature and Ionic Strength :

The volume of aqueous phase can vary between 10 and 70 ml without affecting adduct formation and extraction. A shaking period of 1 min was sufficient for complete extraction of vanadium. Prolonged extraction has no adverse effect on per cent extraction of vanadium. The adducts are stable at least for 36 hr in the temperature range 20-35°. Adjustment of ionic strength of the aqueous phase at 3.5M with respect to potassium chloride or sodium chloride has no effect on efficiency of extraction.

Molar Absorptivity, Sensitivity, Precision and Adherence to Beer's law :

The molar absorptivities, sensitivities and precisions of the present systems are shown in Table 1. The vanadium ranges which adhere to Beer's law are also presented in Table 1.

Stoichiometry of Vanadium-HCPMCPH-PhOH Complexes :

The ratio of vanadium to HCPMCPH was determined by Job's method of continuous

variations¹⁸ and mole ratio method¹⁹. The ratio of vanadium to phenol was determined from slope of the graphical plot of log absorbance versus log concentration of phenol in presence of constant excess of hydroxyamidine²⁰. The results indicate the formation of 1 : 2 : 1 vanadium : HCPMCPH : phenol adduct. The probable overall reaction of the formation of the adducts can be represented as :

Subscripts O and HOAm denote organic phase and hydroxyamidine respectively.

Effect of Diverse Ions :

Fairly large amounts of chloride, bromide, iodate, nitrate, sulfate, fluoride, phthalate, citrate, tartrate, borate, selenate, triethanolamine, urea, thiourea, alkali metals, alkaline earths and lanthanoid elements do not interfere with the determination of 3.2 ppm of vanadium(V) at pH 1.5 ± 0.2 employing vanadium-HCPMCPH-phenol system. The interference of iron(III) was eliminated by masking it with trisodium phosphate. The tolerance limits(ppm) of other ions are shown below :

Fe³⁺(800), Cu²⁺(400), Ni²⁺(600), Co²⁺(660),
Al³⁺(500), Cr³⁺(400), Mn²⁺(400), Pb²⁺(700),
Cd²⁺(600), Zn²⁺(600), Bi³⁺(500), Sb³⁺(500),
Ti³⁺(800), Th⁴⁺(600), Zr⁴⁺(80), Ti⁴⁺(100),
Nb⁵⁺(100), Ta⁵⁺(100), Mo⁶⁺(240), U⁶⁺(500),
W⁶⁺(10).

Determination of Vanadium Content of Steels :

Two tungsten-vanadium steels 64a and 241/1 and a low alloy steel 252 obtained from Bureau of Analyzed Samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, Yorks were selected for the purpose.

Procedure :

An accurately weighed amount of the steel containing approximately 2 mg of vanadium was dissolved in 40 per cent nitric acid. Tungsten was removed as hydrated tungstic oxide by filtration through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The precipitate was washed with hot dilute nitric acid and hydrochloric acid. The combined filtrate was evaporated to near dryness for 2-3 times and diluted to 250 ml with water in a volumetric flask. A 10 ml aliquot was pipetted and vanadium was extracted and determined according to the procedure described earlier. The results are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN SOME STEELS

Steel No. and name	Vanadium certified value %	Vanadium found ^b %
64a Alloy Steel	1.570	1.554
241/1 High Speed Steel	1.570	1.556
252 Low Alloy Steel	0.460	0.451

b=an average of 6 determinations.

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